

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS.
PART V. COPPER AND NICKEL *METAPHENYLENE-*
DIBIGUANIDINE AND THEIR SALTS

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*meta*Phenylenedibiguanide has been found to serve as a quadridentate molecule furnishing four points of attachment to a central metallic atom like copper and nickel. In the present paper a number of complex copper and nickel *metaphenylenedibiguanide* salts, besides the free bases, have been described, and the constitution of the complex discussed.

In course of a series of investigations on the complex compounds of metallic elements with biguanide and its substitution products, it is now found that *metaphenylenedibiguanide* (I) serves as a quadridentate molecule furnishing four points of attachment to a central metallic atom. Instances of quadridentate molecules in literature are rather few in number. Mention may be made of ethylenediamine-bisacetylacetone (Morgan and Main Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2030), 2:2':2'':2'''-tetrapyridyl (Morgan and Bursall, *ibid.*, 1937, 1649), $\beta\beta'\beta''$ -triaminotriethylamine (Pope and Mann, *ibid.*, 1925, 834), ethylene bithioglycolic ether (Reihlen, *Annalen*, 1926, 448, 31a), oxynaphthaldehyde ethylene, or *orthophenylenediamine* and the corresponding salicylaldehyde derivatives (Pfeiffer and Glaser, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 188, 265). Porphyrin derivatives (chlorophyll and haemin) and phthalocyanine also belong to this class. *meta*Phenylenedibiguanide metal complex (II) presents certain interesting features from stereochemical point of view.

(I)

(II)

The central metal atom forms, as it were, the common link for the three fused six membered rings. If the 4-covalent metal atom forms, as supported by a large mass of physical and chemical evidences in the case of nickel and copper, a planar configuration, then this may either be in the same plane with the benzene ring or in a different one. In the former the fused ring (3) will be of irregular shape with a re-entrant angle, in the latter it will have a fold on one side. The tetrahedral configuration of copper in this case, resulting from the possible distortion of the ring due to partial dissymmetry of the molecule, is not, therefore, altogether excluded.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Copper metaPhenylenedibiguanidine and its Hydroxide.—*meta*Phenylenedibiguanide hydrochloride was prepared by heating in aqueous solution 1 mole of *metaphenylenediamine* hydrochloride and 2 moles of dicyandiamide. After the reaction the solution was made alkaline

with ammonia and precipitated by ammoniacal copper sulphate solution. The crude complex sulphate was dissolved in the least quantity of dilute HCl and the complex base was precipitated from the solution by an excess of caustic potash. The precipitate was allowed to settle on the water-bath. This was washed and redissolved in the least amount of HCl and reprecipitated by KOH. The precipitate was then washed with hot water and dried over KOH. {Found: N, 36'92; Cu, 16'92, 16'96; H₂O, 9'58 (by loss at 110°). [Cu. Phen (BigH⁺)₂] (OH)₂ requires N, 37'47; Cu, 17'02; H₂O, 9'64 per cent}.

The base was also prepared by the addition of KOH to a solution of the complex chloride. It forms dull brick-red powder, soluble partially in hot water, but readily in dilute mineral acids with decomposition. The substance is freely soluble in alcohol.

At about 110° it loses two molecules of water forming the anhydro-base, copper *meta*-phenylenedibiguanidine, [Cu.Phen (Big)₂]. Phen(BigH)₂=one molecule of *meta*phenylene-dibiguanide.

The Complex Chloride.—The crude complex base, obtained by precipitation with KOH from an acid (HCl) solution of the crude sulphate, was suspended in water and treated with an excess NH₄Cl solution on the water-bath, till evolution of ammonia ceased. The resulting solution was left in the cold for several hours to crystallise. The product was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. {Found: N, 32'0; Cl, 16'35, 16'40; Cu, 14'66, 14'51. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂] Cl₂. 1½ H₂O requires N, 32'0; Cl, 16'20; Cu, 14'53 per cent}.

The substance forms dark blue-violet crystals, soluble in water and reacts neutral to litmus in the cold.

Equivalent Conductivity at 32'6°

Dilution in litres ...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ ...	105'9	112'6	120'6	127'3	132'9	138'7
Λ _∞ (mean) ...	137'35, from Walden's formula, Λ _∞ =Λ _v (1+n ₁ ⁺ n ₂ ⁺ 0'692v ^{-½}).					

Hence the mobility of the complex [Cu. Phen (BigH⁺)₂] ion=137'35-86'0=51'35 at 32'6°. The substance hydrolyses slightly on dilution and reacts acid to litmus. This is also evident from the conductivity figures.

The *complex bromide* was prepared from a solution of the complex chloride and a cold concentrated solution of potassium bromide. The mixture was allowed to stand in the cold for several hours. The crystals were filtered, washed with ice-cold water and dried in air. {Found: Br, 30'09; Cu, 11'96. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂]Br₂. 2H₂O requires Br, 29'82; Cu, 11'87 per cent}. It forms violet crystals, difficultly soluble in water.

The *complex iodide* was obtained from the complex chloride and potassium iodide as in the previous case. {Found: I, 42'60; Cu, 10'74, 10'78. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂] I₂ requires I, 42'76; Cu, 10'71 per cent}. The substance forms dirty blue-violet crystals, moderately soluble in water.

The *complex nitrate* was prepared from a cold strong solution of the complex chloride and that of ammonium nitrate. The red-violet crystalline precipitate was washed and dried. {Found: Cu, 13'58, 13'61; NO₂, 26'13. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂](NO₂)₂. ½H₂O requires Cu, 13'46; NO₂, 26'24 per cent}.

The *complex sulphate* was prepared from a hot solution of the complex chloride and that of sodium sulphate. The mixture was digested on the water-bath till the precipitate turned deep blue. This was washed with hot water, followed by alcohol and then dried in air. {Found:

Cu, 12'16, 12'18; SO₄, 18'14. [Cu.Phen(BigH⁺)₂] SO₄, $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires Cu, 12'10; SO₄, 18'25 per cent}. The substance forms deep blue crystals, sparingly soluble in water.

The *complex thiosulphate* was obtained as a dull violet crystalline precipitate from a cold solution of the complex chloride and that of sodium thiosulphate. It was washed and dried. {Found: Cu, 12'77, 12'72; S₂O₃, 22'36. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂]S₂O₃, $2\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires Cu, 12'80; S₂O₃, 22'56 per cent}.

The *complex thiocyanate* was prepared by adding an ice-cold solution of the complex chloride to that of an excess of ammonium thiocyanate. The mixture was cooled in ice. The resulting precipitate was washed with ice cold water and dried in air. It forms light greyish blue crystals, soluble in water and alcohol. It hydrolyses rather readily in a warm dilute aqueous solution. {Found: Cu, 13'51; S, 13'34. [Cu.Phen (BigH⁺)₂] (SCN)₂, H₂O requires Cu, 13'43; S, 13'52 per cent}.

Nickel meta-Phenylenedibiguanidine and its Hydroxide.—The complex base was prepared in the same way as the corresponding copper compound, using a solution of nickel sulphate in place of the copper salt. A little ammonium chloride was added before precipitating the base with caustic alkali to prevent precipitation of any nickel hydroxide. The substance forms buff-coloured crystals with a dull red tinge. It is insoluble in water, but slightly soluble in alcohol. {Found: N, 34'73; Ni, 14'35. [Ni. Phen (BigH⁺)₂] (OH)₂, 2H₂O requires N, 34'60; Ni, 14'50 per cent}.

It loses the two molecules of water of hydration (8'82%) at 85°-90° and the remaining two molecules of hydroxylic water at 110° forming the dehydrated base and the anhydro-base—nickel *m*-phenylenedibiguanidine—[Ni. Phen (Big)₂], respectively.

Nickel m-Phenylenedibiguanidinium Sulphate.—The crude sulphate, as obtained during the previous preparation was dissolved in a little dilute H₂SO₄ and reprecipitated by the addition of ammonia, care being taken that the solution did not become alkaline. The precipitate was washed free from sulphate with cold water and then dried in air. {Found: Ni, 11'33; SO₄, 18'75. [Ni. Phen (BigH⁺)₂] SO₄, 5H₂O requires Ni, 11'27; SO₄, 18'44 per cent}.

The substance forms brown crystals, insoluble in water and alcohol.

Attempts to prepare the corresponding complex chloride led, however, to impure products, as the compound hydrolyses in aqueous solution and forms an oily or viscous mass. Neutralisation of the base with dilute HCl, followed by evaporation of the resulting solution to dryness, produced also no better results.